

The Approach Of Supply And Demand Parties To Second-Hand Clothing In The Context Of Ethical Fashion

Etik Moda Bağlamında İkinci El Giysiye Arz-Talep Taraflarının Yaklaşımı

Nisa Nur Duman / Lect. (PHD Stu.)

Istanbul Beykent University, Vocational School, Fashion Design
nisanurduman@beykent.edu.tr

Şerife Gülcü Yıldız / Assoc. Prof. Dr.

Selçuk University, Faculty of Architecture and Design
sgulcu@selcuk.edu.tr

Abstract

In recent years, arising from the fact that societies have realized the harmful impacts of consumption on the environment, ethics and sustainability have gained more significance. The increase in the second-hand consumption market has gained momentum based on the fact that both demand and supply components started to become conscious of these factors, acting in this direction in their shopping preferences. The aim of this research is to reveal the approaches of supply and demand parties in second-hand clothing stores to the concept of sustainability within the scope of ethical fashion and the reasons concerning selling and buying second-hand products. The population of the research consists of store owners/employees selling second-hand clothes in Kadıköy, Balat, and Galata regions in Istanbul and consumers making their purchases from these stores. In the study, the study group was determined by the criterion sampling technique, one of the purposeful sampling methods.

The data of this research carried out by utilizing qualitative research methods, were collected with a semi-structured interview form. The interview questions were prepared by consulting expert opinion. The study data were evaluated by content analysis and MAXQDA 2022 package program was used in the evaluation and coding of the data. When the obtained data was analyzed, it was found that the reasons for the second-hand clothing preference of the participants constituting the supply and demand sides were primarily economic reasons, followed by sustainable environment awareness.

Keywords: Sustainability, ethical fashion, second-hand clothing, supply and demand.

JEL Codes: L67, S56, Q01

Özet

Son yıllarda tüketimin çevreye olan zararlı etkilerinin toplum tarafından fark edilmeye başlaması ile birlikte etik ve sürdürülebilirlik konuları hızla öne çıkmaktadır. Arz taraflarının olduğu kadar talep taraflarının bu konular ile ilgili bilinçlenmeye başlaması ve alışveriş tercihlerinde bu doğrultuda hareket etmeye başlaması ile ikinci el tüketim piyasasında artış meydana gelmiştir. Bu araştırmanın amacı, ikinci el giysi satan mağazalardaki arz ve talep taraflarının etik moda kapsamında yer alan sürdürülebilirlik kavramına yaklaşımlarını ve ikinci el ürün satma ve alma nedenlerini ortaya koymaktır. Araştırmanın evrenini, İstanbul ilinde yer alan Kadıköy, Balat ve Galata bölgelerinde ikinci el giysi satışı yapan mağaza sahipleri/çalışanları ve bu mağazalardan alışveriş yapan tüketiciler oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmada, çalışma grubunun amaçlı örnekleme yöntemlerinden ölçüt örnekleme tekniği ile belirlenmiştir. Nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden faydalanılarak gerçekleştirilen bu araştırmanın verileri, yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formu ile toplanmıştır. Araştırmacılar tarafından geliştirilen görüşme sorularının hazırlanması sırasında alanda uzman akademisyenlerin görüşlerine başvurulmuş ve gerekli düzenlemelerin ardından sorulara son şekli verilerek araştırmaya başlanmıştır. Çalışma verileri içerik analizi ile değerlendirilmiş olup, verilerinin değerlendirilmesi ve kodlanmasında MAXQDA 2022 paket programı kullanılmıştır. Elde edilen bulgular incelendiğinde arz ve talep taraflarını oluşturan katılımcıların ikinci el giysi tercih nedenlerinin öncelikli olarak ekonomik sebepler ardından ise sürdürülebilir çevre bilinci olduğu görülmüştür.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sürdürülebilirlik, etik moda, ikinci el giysi

JEL Kodları: L67, S56, Q01

1. Introduction

As one of the oldest and largest sectors in the world, the textile and fashion industry is an indispensable part of people's daily lives, nonetheless, it is one of the sectors causing the most damage to the environment in the production and consumption phases. This sector is the second largest industry worldwide with the amount of water used in production processes and the chemical ratios released to the environment. The rapid growth and expansion of the sector within the last twenty years have brought the sector to an unsustainable status. Clothing production has approximately doubled owing to the growing middle-class population worldwide and increasing per capita sales in developed economies. On the other hand, with the increase in the number of collections and low prices, the concept of "fast fashion" in the textile and fashion world has taken producers to the final level of the linear production and consumption system (Gabriel & Delgado Luque, 2020: 21). It is believed that the solution to eradicating environmental and social problems caused by the global market will only be feasible if more companies and consumers adopt and implement sustainable strategies (Dağcı Büyük, Ünal & Erciş, 2020: 1159).

Bringing together the concepts of sustainable development and fashion, despite the fact that the concept of "sustainable fashion" has been contradictory until recently, it is of vital importance today. In "Our Common Future", also known as the Brundtland Report published by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987), the concept of sustainable development is defined as "development that meets the needs of present generations without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to meet their own needs". In the report, it is mentioned that to achieve sustainable development, three vital dimensions, namely environmental, social, and economic, should be emphasized simultaneously (Sætra, 2022: 2). A negative change in any of these components implies that the other two dimensions may also encounter long-term losses. For this reason, sustainability may suffer serious damage as the balance between dimensions will be disturbed (Özender Yücel, 2022: 9). Although the goal of sustainability in fashion is quite clear, the methods of achieving sustainability are not clear. Sustainable fashion is a complex endeavor involving many idealisms, but many of its elements need to be considered on a practical level (Aakko & Koskennurmi-Sivonen, 2013: 14).

Throughout history, people have often had difficulties accessing clothes. Since clothes produced from natural resources were limited and limited production was allowed for bartering, people had very few clothes in ancient times. Due to these constraints, clothing production was essentially ecologically sustainable through the artisanal production system.

Throughout the long history of mankind, the global circulation of clothing has been a key force in economic globalization (Brooks, 2015: 8). Today, rapid and dynamic garment production driven by cutting-edge technologies has many negative environmental and social impacts occurring within the product life cycle (Parthiban, Srikrishnan & Kandhavadi, 2017: 9). For each garment purchased, more than the price tag is paid considering factors such as the reduction of resources as a result of overconsumption, environmental pollution, and labor force exploitation. The fashion industry has increasingly complicated the environmental and social relationships over the past fifty years by adopting a "fast fashion" business model and moving its production processes from the north to the south and east in search of low labor costs. This has increasingly complicated the environmental and social relationships over the past fifty years (Köse & Aydın, 2020: 89).

The fashion industry has determined the "fast fashion" business model in the last fifty years and has largely moved its production from the north to the south and east in search of low operating costs, thus the relationships on the environment and social society have become even more complicated.

The textile and fashion industry employs twenty-five million people worldwide and is a source of livelihood for societies, also contributing to women's independence and the establishment of important infrastructures in underdeveloped countries. Thus, fashion can be seen as a vibrant and innovative economic and socio-cultural field offering values at individual, social, institutional and national levels. The easy accessibility of fashion, its emotional language along with its central role in identity formation and communication experiences position it as the driving force of consumption and potentially as a means of change, nevertheless, the harmful impacts of clothing on the deterioration of natural systems due to its relatively high carbon footprint is also increasing (Fletcher & Tham, 2015).

In this study, second-hand clothing consumption is discussed in the context of ethical fashion and its importance for sustainability. Second-hand product consumption has made rapid progress in recent years. The behavior of using second-hand products appears as a process consisting of resale, recycling, gifting, exchange and reuse activities of consumers. Consumers obtain second-hand products through sales channels consisting of online sales sites, flea markets as well as vintage stores.

The aim of this research is to reveal the approaches of supply and demand parts in second-hand product markets to the concept of sustainability within the scope of ethical fashion and the reasons for selling and buying second-hand products. In the research conducted for this purpose, after explaining the relationship between sustainability and ethical fas-

The Approach Of Supply And Demand Parties To Second-Hand Clothing In The Context Of Ethical Fashion

tion, the opinions of the supply parties selling second-hand clothes and the demand parties buying second-hand clothes were evaluated in light of the data collected.

Sub-objectives

1. To reveal the reasons of second-hand clothing sellers for selling second-hand products,
2. To reveal the reasons for second-hand product preference by consumers,
3. To reveal the level of knowledge of second-hand clothing supply and demand parties regarding the concept of ethical fashion,
4. To reveal the demand intensity of second-hand clothing,
5. To reveal the approaches of second-hand clothing consumers towards their old and worn clothes.

The Concept of Sustainability

In recent years, it is seen that many researchers have addressed the environmental sustainability problems and social responsibility concerns of the fashion industry in comprehensive studies carried out on sustainability. Sustainable fashion, which emerged as a movement against the use of clothes harming the environment, unnecessary shopping, the injustice against the labor force working in production, wasting water and energy, is achieved by including the people, processes and the natural environment in the system (Janigo, Wu & DeLong, 2017: 256). Due to negative environmental impacts and lack of sustainability, changes in consumption behavior need to be directed toward reducing, recycling and reusing. For decades many countries have tried to change misuse and overconsumption by establishing sustainable practices in various fields, including the fashion industry. The expansion of the fashion industry is driven by the growth of economies and the global population, as well as fast fashion cycles (Yoo, Jung, & Oh, 2021: 2584). However, the fashion industry has faced many environmental and social challenges arising from a global network of suppliers, manufacturers, retailers, transport companies, and warehouses involved in the complex supply chain structure (Fletcher, 2014: 169).

Environmental and human health risks arise at the very beginning of the fashion life cycle and continue to exist. Toxic chemicals in pesticides have increased yields in conventional cotton production, but have caused illness and death among workers, especially in countries with inadequate environmental regulations. In addition, fabric dyeing and other finishing processes use harmful chemicals polluting great amounts of water. Concerns have also been raised about workers' welfare and social rights in garment

factories, with problems of forced labor, exploitation of child labor and safety violations (Janigo, Wu & De Long, 2017: 259).

According to a study conducted by Cambridge University on sustainable clothing, it is observed that approximately 2.15 million tonnes of clothes are purchased annually and 1.1 million tonnes of clothes are thrown away. In order to shed light on the mentioned amount, it is worth mentioning that one tonne of clothing fits in approximately 200 large garbage bags. For this reason, instead of throwing away clothes, it is increasingly necessary to get rid of habits, reduce purchases, and search for ways to reuse old clothes (Tekin Akbulut, 2012: 40). The concept of sustainable fashion is not limited to the purchasing process, it encompasses the post-purchase phase as well. The post-purchase phase is concerned with whether the consumer reuses, recycles, or simply throws away the garments (Başar, 2022: 17).

Sustainable design in fashion needs to comprise not only economic but also cultural, social, ethical and environmental values. In order to establish the concept of sustainability in the fashion sector, fashion designers, manufacturers, the market and consumers need to change their behavior (Mangır, 2016: 148). In parallel with this objective, designers tend to design using the cradle-to-cradle model, which directs them to design a product considering all stages of the garment's life cycle, including what happens to the garment when it is dispensed or discarded (Başar, 2022: 10).

Sustainability and Ethical Fashion Relationship

The concept of ethics is one of the basic elements of sustainable fashion. In the discipline of sustainable fashion, it is necessary to delineate certain ethical values to tackle current ecological problems. Consumers are less aware of the environmental and social aspects of their fashion choices (Connell, 2011). Fashion production is a long, complex and exploitative process involving collective labor abuses such as low wages, overtime hours, ignored trade union rights, illegal child labor, etc, also being considered one of the largest industrial polluters (Başar, 2022).

When the issue of sustainability in the clothing and textile sector is approached from the consumer perspective, it is seen that consumers are turning towards sustainable or environmental products with the increase in their awareness and concerns about environmental issues. However, sustainable consumption does not adequately affect the clothing purchasing decisions individuals make. Because individuals find sustainable clothing products quite costly, they think there are few product options and that the products have some disadvantages concerning the aesthetic and functional aspects (Büyüç, 2022: 10).

Ünal & Erciş, 2020).

Clothing choice often reflects the identity of consumers and identity is of high significance as far as the fashion consumers are concerned. Therefore, sustainable and ethical factors are not taken into consideration by consumers in their purchasing decisions, which implies that encouraging consumers' environmental interest and sustainable purchasing behaviours in the clothing and textile sector is important for promoting sustainable consumption (Büyük, Ünal, & Erciş, 2020). In this context, the ethical fashion concept is among the orientations of individuals with social awareness and social responsibility. Issues such as how the clothes are produced, by whom and under what conditions, whether an environmentalist approach is observed during the period from production to consumption, and if textile raw materials are examined under the ethical fashion concept (Tekin Akbulut, 2012).

Considering the fact that there is no single industry standard, Ethical fashion is difficult to define. Moreover, it often has characteristics in common with other movements such as fair trade, ecology or green fashion. Ethical Fashion is an all-encompassing term describing ethical fashion design, production, retailing and purchasing. It covers a range of issues such as working conditions, exploitation, fair trade, sustainable production, environment and animal welfare (Parthiban, Srikrishnan & Kandhavadi, 2017). The principle is to source garments ethically while ensuring charitable labor standards and conditions for workers and a sustainable business model in the source country. In addition, organic material is used to minimize the impact on the environment. As a result, ethical fashion can be defined as fashionable garments that combine fair trade principles with sweatshop-free working conditions that by using biodegradable and organic cotton do not harm the environment or workers (Joergens, 2006: 361). There are a number of negative environmental consequences associated with the production processes that take place before consumers acquire and use apparel, including reduced biodiversity, air, water and soil quality and increased greenhouse gas emissions, depleted water resources and other renewable resources, as well as diminishing non-renewable resources. Therefore, the negative environmental impacts of garment and textile production are also indirect environmental impacts of garment consumption (Connell, 2011: 62).

Second-Hand Clothing Consumption

One approach for consumers to promote sustainability in fashion is to use second-hand clothing. Second-hand clothing is an example of recycling extending its useful life. Second-hand shopping also reduces the amount of discarded clothing sent to landfills through reuse and the negative environ-

mental impact caused by the accumulation of textile waste. Second-hand shopping also provides a sense of adventure and a valuable shopping experience at a low cost. For consumers, second-hand shopping is a way of creating and expressing a socially conscious self (Başar, 2022: 15). Items used before by at least one person are defined as second-hand goods. Clothing items have a large share in the second-hand goods market, which is usually evaluated together with antique, retro and vintage products (Deniz, 2020: 1493).

Analyzing the historical process of second-hand consumption, it is observable that it has existed for a long time in Europe and America. When the related field studies are analyzed, it is determined that second-hand consumption is divided into three periods. The period when second-hand consumption emerged and spread in the 18th and 19th centuries, the period when it fell out of favour in the 20th century and finally the 21st century when it regained popularity. When these periods are analyzed, it is revealed that factors such as the Industrial Revolution, capitalism and mass production in the 20th century gave momentum to production-consumption relations, and in the following period, the understanding of producing and consuming was replaced by the perception of consumption beyond compulsory needs. As a consequence of this awareness, second-hand consumption has attained popularity (İşçioğlu & Yurdakul, 2018: 254). Today, the second-hand clothing trade in Western societies is dominated by mostly non-profit charitable organisations and recycling firms, both in domestic and foreign markets. In recent years, growing environmental concerns in the West have increased both the profitability and the prestige of this trade besides giving its practitioners a new prestige as textile rescuers and waste recyclers (Palmer & Clark, 2005).

Many American and European tourists who have recently travelled to African cities have noticed that used clothes from Western countries are being sold in clothing markets. In developed and wealthy countries thousands of kilometres away, such as the United States and the United Kingdom, very few people contemplate what happens to their clothes after they have disposed of them or given them to a recycling company or charity. Many of these clothes end up in stalls in third-world countries. Many people maintain that they did not realise the fact that instead of reaching those in need, their unworn/out-of-fashion clothes were being sold in Africa and that companies were making significant profits. The international trade in second-hand clothes is a counter-current to the flow of new clothes, but it only makes sense if it is considered in harmony with the production of new clothes and what is known as fast fashion (Brooks, 2015: 3). Reusing clothes is associated with reducing the amount of discarded clothing and thus reducing environmental pollution. Second-hand and vintage

The Approach Of Supply And Demand Parties To Second-Hand Clothing In The Context Of Ethical Fashion

clothing is becoming more and more popular nowadays, both for the environmental benefits and for personal style (Park & Lin, 2020: 625). In addition, the second-hand clothing trade has changed its dimension with the opening of "vintage" stores, online sales channels and clothing libraries. Affected by the impact of digitalisation, online channels for second-hand clothing sales are growing 4 times faster than traditional retailing, in this respect, resale also encourages the production of durable products as only products designed for longevity create resale opportunities (Atalay Onur, 2020: 29).

2. Method

In this part of the study, the research model, study group, data collection tool and data analysis are presented.

This study, which was conducted with a qualitative research method, has a case study design. Qualitative research regularly seeks answers by examining different social environments and the groups or individuals constituting these environments. In addition, qualitative techniques allow researchers to share in other people's understandings and perceptions and to explore how people structure and give meaning to their daily lives (Berg & Lune, 2019: 13). The case study within the qualitative research method is defined as a qualitative in-depth investigation of one or more explanatory situations (Berg & Lune, 2019: 14). It ensures that the current phenomenon is dealt with in its real context (Akdemir & Kılıç, 2021: 489).

The universe of the study consists of second-hand stores and consumers who shop for second-Hand Clothes in Istanbul Province. Criterion sampling method, which is one of the purposeful sampling methods, was used to determine the sample group of the study. Purposive sampling helps the researcher to reach important sources of information on the subject, event or phenomenon to be investigated and allows in-depth examination of the situations to be investigated (Akdemir & Kılıç, 2021: 489). In the criterion sampling method, the main purpose is to form the sample from people, events, objects or situations with the qualifications determined in relation to the problem (Büyüköztürk, et. al.,2009). The first criterion of the study group determined by the criterion sample method the Kadıköy, Balat and Galata regions in the province of Istanbul, where there is a high density of second-hand clothes shopping, have been selected. The main criterion determined by the researchers in the selection of the stores where the application will be carried out in this research has been specified above, and the fact that the consumers participating in the research are shopping in the stores in the specified regions has been determined as the second criterion. Accordingly, the sample group consists of a total of 21

volunteer participants, 8 store owners / employees / supply side and 13 consumers / demand side who shop in these stores. The interviews were conducted with a semi-structured interview form and lasted an average of 15 minutes. The aim of the study is to select the regions with different sociocultural structures where second-hand shopping is intense and the stores that are of great interest to consumers in these regions. In this context, the study is limited to the questions in the semi-structured interview form and 8 store owners / employees / supply side and 13 consumers / demand side who shop from these stores in Kadıköy, Balat and Galata regions in Istanbul.

In the study, as data collection tools, an 11-item semi-structured interview form for supply sides and a 13-item semi-structured interview form for consumers developed by the researchers were used.

The interview questions were prepared compatible to be conducted with this type of interview technique. These questions were asked to the interviewees in the same order, but the interviewee is allowed to answer the questions as broadly as he/she wishes during the interview (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011). In order to ensure the internal validity of the prepared interview form and to check to what extent it serves the purpose, its comprehensibility and applicability, it was submitted to the opinions of academicians who are experts in their fields. In line with the feedback from the experts, the questions in the interview form were corrected and applied to the sample.

In order to ensure external validity, the researcher who will carry out a study by utilizing qualitative research methods should inform the research participants about all stages of the research (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011: 257). For this reason, detailed explanations were given to the participants at all stages of the research. The participants were not forced to participate in the research and participation was voluntary.

The validity and reliability of the research were ensured by giving in-depth profiles of the study area and the participants in the research, as well as trying to ensure the consistency of the data within themselves (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011). In addition, the fact that the two researchers conducting this research reviewed all the data several times and made a joint decision, to make the research reliable. The interview questions were directed to each participant with the same words and intonations to evoke the same meaning. After data collection, the answers were categorised by coding method. Firstly, the data were transcribed and then the findings were interpreted. According to the ethics of scientific research, the names of the participants were kept confidential and could not be deciphered anywhere in the study. The participant store owners/supply parts A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6; consumers/demand sides T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6

and the data were recorded in PDF format.

The data obtained from the interview form in the study group were analyzed using descriptive analysis and content analysis techniques. In the descriptive analysis approach, the aim is to present the obtained data to the reader in a regulated and interpreted state (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011). Content analysis is the organization and interpretation of similar data in an understandable form by bringing together similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes (Creswell, 2013). Defined as a research technique used to make repeatable and valid inferences from the text, the Content analysis technique provides information on practical actions by increasing the researcher’s understanding of specific facts and events (Polat, 2020). For this reason, it was aimed to obtain a meaningful result by coding the answers given by the participants to the interview questions within the scope of the subject. The answers given by the participants constituting the supply and demand sides to the questions in the semi-structured interview form were recorded on the form. The data obtained from the form were arranged in the Office programme and coding was created within the content. MAXQDA 2022, a qualitative data analysis programme, was used for content analysis. Qualitative analysis software packages provide various visual display possibilities to help researchers explore and analyze data and present relationships (Berg & Lune, 2019: 375).

3. Findings

In order to ensure coding reliability, all interview data were coded by the researchers, and 6 interview forms randomly selected by two independent academicians working in the field of qualitative research methods were coded separately and the codes performed by the independent academicians, and the researchers were compared. According to the formula of consensus/(consensus+disagreement)*100 suggested by Miles and Huberman (1994), the consensus between the coders was calculated as 100% (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

Demographic data

Demographic data on the supply parties participating in the research are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1. Supply Side Demographic Data

Participant	Age	Gender	Sector Experience	Second-Hand Clothing Sales Experience Year
A1	51	F	30	2
A2	69	M	45	4

A3	26	F	2	2
A4	22	F	3	3
A5	35	F	15	8
A6	27	M	2	1
A7	21	F	2	2
A8	30	M	8	18

Demographic data on the demand parties participating in the research are depicted in the Table 2.

Table 2. Demand Side Demographic Data

Participant	Age	Gender	Profession	Education Status
T1	21	M	Model	High School
T2	22	F	Student	Bachelor's Degree
T3	30	M	Editor	B.A
T4	20	F	Graphic Designer	Associate Degree
T5	20	F	Accounting	Associate Degree
T6	18	F	Theatre actor/student	Bachelor Student
T7	36	F	Academician	PhD
T8	22	F	Student	Bachelor's Degree
T9	19	F	Student	Bachelor's Degree
T10	38	F	Academician	PhD
T11	21	F	Student	Associate Degree
T12	19	F	Student	Associate Degree
T13	39	F	Psychologist	Master's Degree

According to Table 1 and Table 2 the majority of the participants in the research are women. The total number of female participants on the supply side and demand side is 16 and constitutes 76.19% of

The Approach Of Supply And Demand Parties To Second-Hand Clothing In The Context Of Ethical Fashion

the total 21 participants. Fifty per cent of the supply providers are between the ages of 26-35. The majority of consumers (69, 23%) are between the ages of 15-25. 46,15% of the consumers are postgraduate and associate degree students.

Questions and Comments for Supply Side

The participants, who constitute the supply side of the research, were first asked the question "Why did you prefer to sell second-hand clothes?". (A1) of the participants (A1) answered "To continue the life of the clothes, especially for economic reasons, to bring clean and usable products together with the consumer, to bring the clothes of the old period fashion together with the consumer", (A2) "It is easy to supply", (A3) "To make old fashioned clothes meet new users", (A4) "Because it is a different and more selective concept", (A5) "In order to contribute to sustainability", (A6) "In order to be ecologically beneficial to the environment", (A7) "The idea that vintage products are of better quality and special", (A8) "I decided to sell the clothes left by the family because I could not afford to throw them away".

In addition to this, when the question "Do you use second-hand clothes besides selling second-hand clothes?" was asked from the supply side participants, all participants stated that many of their clothes are second-hand products either inherited from their families or purchased.

(A1), (A2), (A5), (A8) answered the question "Do you also sell new clothes in the store?" as "No, all products are second hand", (A3), (A4), (A7) stated that "we have our products suitable for the vintage concept" and (A6) stated that all clothes are second-hand products and only accessories (hats, bags, glasses, etc.) are new products.

What is the general product group in your store? (A8) answered the question as all underwear/outerwear, evening dresses, costumes and accessories for women and men, and it was found that the product groups in the stores of all other participants were mainly women/men, upper clothing/lower clothing, daily clothing.

All participants in the study group answered the question "Where do you supply the clothes you sell in your store?" as "The majority of the products are supplied from warehouses located at certain points, especially from warehouses where second-hand products are imported from abroad". In addition to this, it was found out that it was also obtained from flea markets, from the first users who brought and delivered them, and from the unused clothes left by the family.

To the question "Do you also sell clothes through online sales channels?", (A1), (A2) stated that they sell "through Instagram" social media, (A3), (A4),

"through Instagram and website", (A5) "through the website", (A6), "through Instagram and shopping site", (A7) "through Instagram and closet site". Participant (A8) answered the question as "no, we sell all products in our store".

Concerning the question "Why do you think customers prefer second-hand clothes?" are evaluated; it is seen that the majority of the participants gave answers as "economic reasons" and "feeling special". (A1) of the participants (A1) "Economic reasons in the first place, but also to have a unique product", (A5) "First of all, for authenticity, as well as not harming the environment and affordable price". (A4) "They say that it gives a sense of experience", (A6) "Customers think that the clothes have a story and carry traces of the past, and this is more interesting to them", (A4) "Customers think that the clothes have a story and carry traces of the past, and this is more interesting to them", and they also stated that the consumers' sense of experience and the connection of the clothes with the past also affect their preference. In addition, participants (A7) and (A8) stated that "Since second-hand clothes are much more specialised pieces, customers find the pieces produced from selected, quality materials more valuable" and that the fact that the pieces are unique and different from the current fashion is also an important factor in consumers' second-hand clothing preferences.

Regarding the question "Do you know about the concept of sustainability?", it was concluded that (A4) and (A6) of the supply side participants did not have any information. One of the participants (A3) said "Yes, I know the concept of sustainability, I also receive fashion education. The fact that the used products are sustainable and vegan, and local production makes me happy. I make my clothing preferences in this way", while (A5) responded "Yes, the concept of sustainability is our existential reason. In addition, the majority of supply-side participants think that they serve sustainability through the sale of second-hand clothes". Participants (A4) and (A6), who were not informed about the concept, concluded that their supply is actually within the scope of sustainability after being informed about the subject.

In response to the question "Do you have information about the concept of ethical fashion?", only one of the participants (A5) stated that he had information concerning the concept of ethical fashion and that he was trying to act upon this purpose. It was concluded that the other participants did not have information about the concept of ethical fashion, and all participants were informed about the subject.

Finally, the question "The demand of consumers for second-hand clothes and the number of daily sales" was answered by all participants as "the demand is

quite intense". In addition, (A1) "It met the expectation quite well when we consider the average, we saw that there was an intense interest", (A3) "The consumer's interest in second-hand products is quite intense, vintage products are more preferred than brand new products in the store. Especially the customers of this region are fixed customers, they also demand intensively in order to avoid monotonous clothing", (A6) "The interest of consumers is very good, it is expected that there will be a 50% increase in demand by the end of 2024 with the effect of economic factors".

Questions and Comments for the Demand Side

The participants, who constitute the demand side of the research, were first asked the question "Why do you prefer to buy second-hand clothes?". When the answers were analyzed, "being economical", "the importance is given to the environment" and "the ties of the clothes with the past" were the prominent answers. One of the participants (T4) stated that "second-hand clothes are both economically more suitable and more appropriate to be used for a long time because they are of better quality and durable". Similarly, (T12) stated that "it is much more affordable than new clothes, so I can have more clothes" and (T7) stated that "sometimes the product I want is only available as second-hand, so I prefer it. Sometimes the price I can pay for the product I like is only available second-hand, so I prefer it. Even if I can afford it, I may also prefer second-hand, in which I think "Why should I pay so much money when I will wear not long?". On the other hand, one of the participants (T6) answered in line with the importance of sustainability: "I prefer second-hand clothes because I care about the environment, and if the product I want is already available, I think there is no need to bring waste into the cycle by buying a new one". Participants (T1), (T2) and (T8) responded "I feel more emotional because the clothes have a history with their first owners", and "I like the ties with the past", it makes me feel different and special".

To the question "Do you mostly prefer second-hand or new clothes in the clothes you buy?"; 8 participants stated that they "prefer new products more" and 1 participant stated that they "prefer second-hand products more". Participant (T9) explained the reason for second-hand preference as "I prefer second-hand both economically and design-wise. I also find it important in terms of sustainability." The other 4 participants stated that "it varies a lot according to the periods, while in some months they prefer new products, sometimes they buy more second-hand clothes". One of the participants (T3) stated "It can change depending on finding what I am looking for. In some periods, I can buy more second-hand products and in some periods I can buy new products.", (T4) "Of course, I buy new clothes, but my priority is generally vintage stores and flea

markets.", (T7) "In general, my priority is new clothes. But at the same time, I also look for similar ones in second hand."

When we look at the clothing categories particularly preferred by the participants on the demand side; it is seen that they mainly prefer coats, sweaters and dress-style products for outerwear and upper body clothing group, while they prefer trousers and lower group products less. In addition, when the participants were asked "the product group that they would never prefer second-hand", the majority of the participants gave answers such as "underwear, swimwear, socks and pajamas".

"(T2), (T3), (T4), (T10) and (T13) stated that they use the products directly, (T5), (T6), (T8), (T11) and (T12) stated that they make repairs and modifications in case of a worn/damaged product. Among the participants (T1), (T1) stated that "I do not prefer to use it directly, I make changes on it and then use it", (T7) stated that "I can use some products directly, but after using the product for a while, I can make changes on it - in line with my skill - so that I can wear it for a longer period of time", (T9) stated that "I make some fixing on some pieces according to my style. For example, if I find the jacket long, I have it shortened, I make a bag out of jeans."

As for the question "Do you have knowledge about the concept of sustainability? , it is seen that (T1), (T3), (T4), (T5), (T6), (T7), (T8), (T9), (T11), (T12), and (T13) of the demand side participants stated that they have knowledge about sustainability. In addition, (T1); "Many designers follow sustainable clothing collections, second-hand clothing markets also support this issue." (T9); "Producing products with a more environmentally friendly approach with respect to fast fashion.", (T11); "Contributing to our world ecologically by extending the life cycle of products.", (T12); "To continue the life cycle of a product. To reuse it, to reduce its harm to the environment.". Based on the answers obtained from other participants, it was concluded that (T2), (T3), (T4), (T10) and (T13) did not have much information, and (T10) of the participants did not know the concept of sustainability.

To the question "Are you familiar with the concept of ethical fashion?"; (T1), (T2) and (T5) stated that they had not heard of the concept before and did not have any information, while (T3), and (T6) stated that they had very little information. On the other hand, it was concluded that (T4), (T7), (T8), (T9), (T10), (T11), (T12), and (T13) participants had knowledge about the concept of ethical fashion. According to the answers given by the participants (T7); "Ethical fashion can be explained as prioritising transparency and sensitivity at every stage from the production of everything in the fashion sector until it reaches the consumer", (T8); "It stipulates that animal skins and furs are not used in textile production." (T9); "Produ-

The Approach Of Supply And Demand Parties To Second-Hand Clothing In The Context Of Ethical Fashion

cing products with a more environmentally friendly approach against fast fashion.”, (T10); “Protection of workers’ rights, companies’ production in accordance with ethical rules while producing.” (T11); “Tests on living things, the effect of chemicals.” (T12), “Environmentally harmless production in terms of sustainability, reducing the damage of chemicals to the environment.”

When the answers given by the participants to the question “How does it make you feel to support sustainable fashion by buying second-hand clothes?” are analyzed (T3); “I do think that consumption is more than necessary. For this reason, I think I make a more useful purchase with second-hand clothes.” (T6); “It makes me feel good because I contribute a little, I think I am doing something useful for the society.” (T7); “When such questions raised, I thought that I support this issue because I was always making such a choice by acting at the point of my sustainability, but I think I will take this point into consideration now thanks to you. I hope I can give more conscious answers in your similar studies from now on.” (T9); “Knowing that I have made a contribution to preventing the destruction of nature makes me feel happy.” (T10); “I feel happy because I don’t pay a lot of money and I can buy the products I want.” (T11); “Making an economic profit makes me feel happy.” (T12); “First of all, I make a profit economically. In addition, knowing that I am beneficial to the environment, consuming this kind of consumption makes me feel psychologically and emotionally happy.” (T13); “I think I strengthen my connection with the past. I like to wear clothes with a story. It excites me and makes me curious. I like to wear a garment for a long time. Thus, I think we increase our responsibility towards the environment.”

When the answers given to the question “Do you think that buying second-hand products reduces the environmental impact of fashion?” are evaluated, it is revealed that the majority of the demand side participants stated that “yes, second-hand clothing consumption is beneficial in preventing the harmful environmental effects of fashion”. Participant (T9) stated that the consumption of second-hand clothes is a beneficial behaviour towards the environment and commented: “Everyone thinks how much contribution can I make with my purchase, but it is a great benefit for the environment that not even a single product goes to waste”. On the other hand, participant (T6) stated; “No, I don’t think so, fast production continues” and (T7) stated that “It would be more accurate to say that I think it should actually decrease in this regard, but I think that fashion continues in the same course, irrespective of being second-hand products or not”.

When the answers to the question “Can you repair your clothes with simple modifications to extend

the life of your clothes or do you have someone else do the repairing?” were analysed, (T1) and (T0) of the participants answered as “no, I do not repair or have someone else repair the worn or damaged clothes”. The other majority of the participants gave the answer “yes, I do alterations or have them modified”. Among the participants (T2); “I cannot do it, but I get help from my family for the repair process”, (T4); “Sometimes when a part of my garment is ripped or torn, I patch it according to the condition of the torn area or I cut the garment into pieces and combine it with my other clothes. This both prolongs the life of my garment and provides me with the opportunity to contribute to sustainability”, (T5); “If it is not in a very bad condition, I repair it, but if I cannot do it, I give it to the tailor to repair it”. (T7); “If I can handle it with my own skills, of course, I repair it or turn it into other things, for example, shorts from jeans or tracksuits with torn hems, turning long-sleeved clothes into short sleeves, sewing small rips. However, if there is a situation I cannot modify and product modification requires mastery, I get professional help. I wear all my clothes as long as they can be worn, and when they become unwearable, that product continues its life as a cleaning cloth for a while. In case of weight gain and loss, if the clothes are still wearable, I can sell them second-hand or give them to people in need”.

The question “Do you find it ethical to produce long-lasting clothes?” was answered as yes by all participants. Among the participants (T1); “Yes, I think that the long-lasting production of clothes is a system that should continue, but it is much more ethical and correct in this period, but I don’t think it can continue much due to the fast fashion system”, (T3); “Yes, I find it more ethical. I don’t like that the clothes wear out very quickly. Clothes that wear out quickly leave consumers in a difficult situation financially and emotionally”, (T4); “Yes, I think it would be healthier if the clothes were produced in long-lasting and limited quantities, I find fast fashion unnecessary”, (T6); “If harmful factors are not used to extend the life of the product, I find it ethical”. (T6); “Here, it is necessary to look at the situation from two sides, it is ethical for the consumer, less money is spent, but in the second direction, there are manufacturers, they may find it profitable to produce shorter-lasting products for their maintenance. Since the situation here changes according to the direction in which it is looked at, maybe we should not look for ethics at this point”. (T8); “Yes, I find it ethical. Even if it is not long-lasting, I think it should be suitable for recycling”. (T9); “I find it ethical, but long-lasting clothes are very expensive financially”. (T11); “Yes, long-lasting clothes are more ethical in terms of ecological and sustainability”.

Table 3. Code Statistics

Table 3 sheds light on the general code statistics. In the table where the usage frequency of the codes between the consumer and supply sides is shown, the code "garment life" is identified with "ethical fashion" in the eyes of consumers. No feedback was received from the consumers on the conceptual definition of "ethical fashion", nonetheless, having made the necessary definition of the concept during the interview, it was concluded that the production of long-lasting clothes was the equivalent of the concept for them. "Do you find the production of long-lasting clothes ethical?" "Yes, long-lasting clothes are more ethical in terms of ecological and sustainability (T-11)", and "It should definitely exist (T-2)". In addition, the vast majority of second-hand clothing supply providers and consumers expressed their second-hand preference with "affordability". While affordability is perceived as "being affordable" by consumers, it is perceived as "affordable price in supply and cheap product due to the harsh economic conditions" by supply parties.

Figure 1 Relationship between Supply and Demand Parties

Figure 1 illustrates the code frequencies of consumers and supply parties by comparing two case models obtained with MAXQDA 2022 package program. Although the relevant figure helps to make general evaluations, the unequal number of participation of consumers and supply sides constitutes a limitation in thorough evaluation. Consumers' perceptions of "ethical fashion" are expressed with the codes "garment life", "budget-friendly", and "budget-hostile". Consumers who find second-hand clothing consumption "economical" also think that it contributes to "sustainability". Although the main

reason for preference is seen as the economy. In response to the question "Why do you prefer to buy second-hand clothes?" consumers responded: "I feel more emotional because the clothes have a history with their first owners. In addition, having more special pieces that not everyone has is also a reason of preference for me (T-2)", "I think I strengthen my connection with the past. I like to wear clothes with a story. It excites me and makes me curious (T-13)", "connection with the past", "finding the design beautiful", "and feeling special". The supply sides were asked the question "Why do you think customers prefer second-hand clothes?" under the same codes and similar answers were received. This similarity between the answers shows that the supply sides recognise their consumers in a sense. Percentage distributions of the codes related to the preference for second-hand clothes by supply and demand sides are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Why do you prefer second-hand clothes?

Codes	Supply Sides	Request Parties
Feeling Special	75,00%	38,50%
Finding Design Beautiful	12,50%	38,50%
Connecting with the Past	62,50%	15,40%
Sustainability	62,50%	84,60%

As the visual expression of the frequency of use of the codes, The code cloud was created separately for supply providers and consumers, as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The sizes and thicknesses of the codes in the code cloud show the frequency of use of the code.

Figure 2 Vocabulary Cloud for Supply Side

Figure 3 Word Cloud on Consumer Parties

4. Conclusion

Second-hand consumption activities associated with low status in the past years have gained significance again today with consumers having more ecological awareness. These consumption activities become much more sustainable if they prevent the purchase of a new product. Consumers considering the resale value of high-quality products can shape their preferences and behaviours accordingly. For example, they may exhibit sustainable consumption behaviour by preferring high-quality and resalable clothes over disposable clothes. In addition to purchasing preferences, changes in consumers' attitudes can also be translated into practical behaviours. Consumers can take better care of the products they use in order to ensure the resale value of the products they buy, thus extending the life cycle of the products (Çelik Varol, 2022: 53).

Billions of second-hand garments are traded worldwide every year, spanning North and South America, connecting Europe to East and West Africa, and stretching across Asia and around the Pacific. Used clothing networks differ from other trade patterns in that they reverse the flow of clothing produced for sale. While new clothes are predominantly produced in low-income countries and emerging economies such as China, used clothes travel from rich countries to poor countries. Moreover, they are bonds of intimate connection, as they physically link consumers wearing new clothes in the global North (Australia, Europe, Japan and North America) with some of the poorest people in the global South (Africa, most of Asia, the Middle East) (Brooks, 2015:4).

The results obtained in line with the findings of this study, which was conducted to determine the approaches of supply and demand sides to second-hand clothing in the context of sustainability and ethical fashion, are as follows. It is observed that second-hand clothing supply parties support the sustainability approach with their answers to the questions posed. When the reasons why the sellers prefer the second-hand market are analyzed, it is seen that in addition to economic reasons, the ea-

sier supply of second-hand products compared to the new products is an important factor for them to operate in the second-hand clothing market. All of the sellers choose their products from imported products from foreign markets. In this way, they can create a special ossified customer group by offering clothes with a higher quality, special and selective concept for consumers. On the other hand, many sellers try to reach more audiences more easily by selling through social media and web pages. These answers of the supply sides, who stated that the reasons for customers' preference for second-hand clothes are primarily economic reasons and then the desire to have unique clothes with a story and experience, are in line with the demand side.

Although only two participants have no knowledge about the concept of sustainability, it is stated in the answers given that all other participants know the concept and that this is one of the purposes of their existence and that they were established to serve this purpose. Contrary to the answers given for the concept of sustainability, it is seen that the supply-side participants do not have much information about the concept of ethical fashion. Only one participant a comprehensive explanation about ethical fashion, and the other participants who could not express an opinion on the subject were explained about ethical fashion, and after the explanation, they stated that they actually serve within the scope of ethical fashion.

Finally, the participants, who stated that consumers are more interested than they expected, put forward the view that this rate will increase even more in the coming years. It is seen that second-hand clothing demand parties support the ethical fashion and sustainability approach with their answers to the questions posed. When the reasons why consumers prefer the second-hand market are analyzed, economic reasons come to the fore. Then, environmental impacts and the ties of the clothes with the past were expressed by many participants. In addition to finding second-hand clothes quite economical compared to new products, consumers also stated that the designs of the clothes produced in the past were more special and emphasized that the raw materials were of much higher quality. Participants mostly prefer upper body and outer garments such as sweaters, shirts, dresses, coats, and it has been observed that they never prefer products such as underwear and swimwear for hygienic purposes.

Some of the participants use second-hand clothes as they are, and some of them state that they make changes on the clothes they buy if they are defective/damaged. In addition, it was concluded that in order to prolong the life of their old or worn-out clothes, they make alterations / have them made or make changes to the products, sometimes even combining two separate products and obtaining a

single product. Old or outdated clothes can be used as new garments or accessories by making some changes on them.

On the demand side, only two participants stated that fast fashion is an ecological threat and does not provide an environmental benefit despite second-hand consumption, while the other participants think that the consumption of second-hand clothes reduces the environmental impact, but it is seen that by consuming second-hand clothes, they care for others and the natural world and feel more special and happy.

Reference

- Aakko, M., & Koskenurmi-Sivonen, R. (2013). Sustainable Fashion Design: Possibilities and Challenges. *Research Journal of Textile and Apparel*, 17(1), 13-22. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/RJTA-17-01-2013-B002>.
- Akdemir, A. B., & Kılıç, A. (2021). Nitel Makalelerin Yöntem Analizi. *Muğla Sıtkı Koçman üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 8(2), 486-502. doi:[10.21666/muefd.834707](https://doi.org/10.21666/muefd.834707).
- Atalay Onur, D. (2020). Moda Tasarımında Döngüsel Ekonomi Kavramı ve Farklı Tasarım Seviyelerinde Benimsenen Stratejiler. *Sanat ve Tasarım Dergisi*, 10(1), 24-40. doi:[10.20488/sanattasarim.828900](https://doi.org/10.20488/sanattasarim.828900).
- Başar, A. (2022). İkinci El Giysi Satışı Yapan İnternet Uygulamalarının İncelenmesi. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Moda Tasarımı Bölümü, Ankara.
- Berg, B. L., & Lune, H. (2019). *Qualitative Research Methods in Social Sciences* (A. Arı , Çev.). in Konya: Eğitim Publishing House.
- Brooks, A. (2015). *Clothing Poverty: The Hidden World of Fast Fashion and Second-hand Clothes*. London: Zed Books. doi:[ISBN: 1783600683,9781783600687](https://doi.org/10.1080/1783600683,9781783600687).
- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Kılıç Çakmak, E., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2009). *Sampling Methods, Scientific Research Methods Book Presentation*.
- Connell, K. Y. (2011). Exploring consumers' perceptions of eco-conscious apparel acquisition behaviours. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 7(1), 61-73. doi:[10.1108/174711111111114549](https://doi.org/10.1108/174711111111114549).
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Method Approaches*. California: SAGE Publications.
- Çelik Varol, M. (2022). Second Hand Consumption as an Example of Sustainability. *Journal of Critical Communication Studies*, 4(1), 51-68. doi:[10.53281/kritik.1130993](https://doi.org/10.53281/kritik.1130993).
- Dağcı Büyük, H., Ünal, S., & Erciş, A. (2020). Sürdürülebilir Giysi Satın Almadaki Etik Unsurların Değerlendirilmesi: Sosyal Ağ Kullanıcıları Üzerine Bir Araştırma. *Eskişehir Osmangazi Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 15(3), 1159-1184. <https://doi.org/10.17153/oguiibf.622873>
- Deniz, E. (2020). Çevrimiçi ikinci-el Giyim Eşyası Satın Almaya Etki Eden Faktörlerin İncelenmesi. *İnsan ve Toplum Bilimleri Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 9(2), 1487-1519. <https://doi.org/10.15869/itobiad.700919>
- Fletcher, K. (2014). *Sustainable Fashion and Textiles, Design Journeys*. (Second Edition). New York: Routledge Taylor & Francis Group. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315857930>.
- Fletcher, K., & Tham, M. (2015). *Routledge Handbook Of Sustainability And Fashion*, First published,. New York: Routledge.
- Gabriel , M., & Delgado Luque, M. L. (2020). Sustainable Development Goal 12 and Its Relationship with the Textile Industry. In M. A. Gardetti, & S. S. Muthu, *The UN Sustainable Development Goals for the Textile and Fashion Industry* (p. 21). Singapore: Textile Science and Clothing Technology, Springer. doi:[DOI: 10.1007/978-981-13-8787-6_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-8787-6_2).

İşçioğlu, T.E. ve Yurdakul D. (2018). İkinci el giyim motivasyonları ve sürdürülebilirlik üzerine keşifsel bir araştırma, *Pazarlama Teorisi ve Uygulamaları Dergisi*, 4(2):253-280.

Janigo, K. A., Wu, J., & DeLong , M. (2017). Redesigning Fashion: An Analysis and Categorisation of Women's Clothing Upcycling Behaviour. *The Journal of Design, Creative Process & the Fashion Industry*, 9(2), 254-279. doi:[10.1080/17569370.2017.1314114](https://doi.org/10.1080/17569370.2017.1314114).

Joergens, C. (2006). Current Research Development Ethical fashion: myth or future trend? *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 10(3), 360-371. doi:[Doi:Doi.org/10.1108/13612020610679321](https://doi.org/10.1108/13612020610679321).

Köse, Ş. G., & Aydın, K. (2020). Sürdürülebilir Moda Perakendiciliği: Tüketici Algıları Üzerine Bir Araştırma. *Istanbul Business Research*, 49(1), 86-116. <http://doi.org/10.26650/ibr.2020.49.0099>

Mangır, A. F. (2016). Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma İçin Yavaş ve Hızlı Moda. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Meslek Yüksekokulu Dergisi*, 19 (41. Özel Sayı) 143-154.

Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative Data Analysis: An Expanded Sourcebook*. California: Sage Publications.

Özender Yücel, B. (2022). İngiltere "Charity Shop" Örneği Üzerinden Türkiye'de Yardım Dernekleri İkinci El Giysi Satış Mağazaları Model Önerisi. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Başkent Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Tekstil ve Moda Tasarımı Ana Bilim Dalı, Ankara.

Palmer, A., & Clark, H. (2005). *Old Clothes, New Looks; Second-Hand Fashion*. Berg Publishers. doi:[ISBN: 1859738575,9781859738573](https://doi.org/10.1080/1859738575,9781859738573).

Park, H. J., & Lin, L. M. (2020). Exploring attitude-behaviour gap in sustainable consumption: comparison of recycled and upcycled fashion products,. *Journal of Business Research*(117), 623-628.

Parthiban, M., Srikrishnan, M. R., & Kandhavadivu, P. (2017). *Sustainability in Fashion and Apparels, Challenges and Solutions*. New Delhi, India: Woodhead Publishing India PVT LTD.

Polat, H. (2020). Halkla İlişkiler Alanındaki Doktora Tezlerinde Yeni Medya Olgusu: Nitel Bir Veri Analizi. *Uluslararası Anadolu Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 4(4), 289-306. <https://doi.org/10.47525/ulasbid.823915>.

Sætra , H. S. (2022, 24 February). *AI For The Sustainable Development Goals*. (First Edition). Boca Raton: CRC Press. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003193180>.

Tekin Akbulut, A. S. (2012). Türkiye'de Etik Moda Üzerine Bir Araştırma. *Akdeniz Üniversitesi, G.S.F., I. Uluslararası Moda ve Tekstil Tasarımı Sempozyumu* , s.s. 39-43. Antalya: Akdeniz Sanat Dergisi.

Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2011). *Sosyal Bilimlerde Nitel Araştırma Yöntemleri* (8. Baskı). Ankara: Seçkin Yayıncılık.

Yoo, F., Jung, H. J., & Oh, K. W. (2021). Motivators and Barriers for Buying Intention of Upcycled Fashion Products in China. *MDPI, Sustainability*, 13(5), 2584-2602. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052584>.